

The HIT2GAP project

Background

HIT2GAP is a four-year project which began in September 2015 and will run to September 2019. Its aim is to reduce the gap between the theoretical energy performance of buildings and the actual consumption in use.

A typical office building will use much more energy than the design team and client expected at the design and construction phases. HIT2GAP is seeking to reduce the gap between the anticipated energy use and what actually happens once a building is occupied. The reasons for 'the gap' are multifarious, ranging from compromises at the design and construction stages, to construction/ detailing and commissioning issues and unexpected user behaviours. Furthermore, renewable energy devices and other building services do not always work well with each other, and this can reduce the overall impact of devices installed to save energy.

HIT2GAP cannot solve all of these problems, and while the project is focused specifically on eliminating energy profligacy in buildings, it also aims to identify other contributory factors.

The main objectives of the project are to:

- reduce the energy performance gap, by focusing on the operational phase of buildings;
- propose a new paradigm for the development of energy management platforms in buildings, integrating simulation modelling, monitoring and behaviour impacts; and to
- provide a marketable, smart platform that can be adopted in any building or group of buildings.

The project was funded through the H2020 EU programme in 2015 and is now in its final year.

The Project

The 21 HIT2GAP partners (commercial and academic) are working to create a new kind of smart energy management platform (an integrated technology concept), which is

both generic, modular, and interoperable and which could be used for a wide variety of buildings and groups of buildings. The approach taken is to build an open, 'plug and play' application-based platform to support a new generation of Building Management Systems (BMS). By this mechanism, it is intended to support user requirements in buildings that are widely diverse. The approach will allow the platform to evolve and remain up-to-date as new and emerging technologies emerge.

The hope is that the results generated by the HIT2GAP project in terms of the reduction in differences between modelled and actual building behaviour may also be of value to the design and construction phases of future buildings.

HIT2GAP aims to build a new generation of building monitoring and control tools based on advanced data treatment techniques, allowing new approaches to assess energy performance, in order to gain a better understanding of the building's behaviour and the role of occupants, ultimately leading to better performance.

HIT2GAP will enhance current BMS functionalities by:

- using alternative sensors and meters (e.g., smart phones, laptops, tablets, smart watches, etc.) to allow the monitoring of spaces without traditional sensors or to extract additional information beyond existing data sources (i.e. disaggregation);
- integrating Data Mining techniques for Knowledge Discovery (DMKD) as a core module for building performance assessment and understanding, and associated predictive maintenance services;
- adding occupants' behaviour to the equation. Taking into account that users play a significant role in building performance, it will be possible to better understand building performance, enhance predictions and control and optimise energy consumption and occupants' comfort, health and well-being;
- providing continuous performance evaluation and improvement based on measured, historical and simulated data coming from a new generation of simulation services;
- integrating demand/supply management tools for building-integrated and community renewable energy sources; and
- adapting the available visualisation interfaces to specific user needs (technical and non-technical profiles) to deliver the information effectively.

Core Platform and Data Collection

The basic H2G structure is as outlined below:

- a **generic, open information platform** (the HIT2GAP Core) that allows connection and communication with HIT2GAP modules, external devices and user interfaces - to collect and store information about a building;
- as well as data storage, the **platform** also provides basic functionalities such as data structuring, data pre-processing (consolidation and alerts, conversion, arithmetic functions, detection of outliers and missing data, extrapolation).

- **simulation modelling**, to establish energy consumption benchmarks (forecasting, benchmarking);
- a variety of **modules** to inform users, energy managers and engineers, presented in a user-friendly format; plus
- **third-party modules** – by providing a smart open platform, external developers will be able to offer up new modules to the core.

The solution will provide:

- a free and open source approach to allow continued development and maintenance of the core HIT2GAP platform;
- a minimum viable product definition of the core platform; plus
- modules that enable the platform to perform value added tasks.

To this end, a core data exchange platform is being established to collect and store data from disparate sources, and deliver subsets of these data to a range of applications (services) intended to support facilities management. The ultimate aim is to identify physical interventions that will alleviate operational problems and so reduce the performance gap.

At the core of the approach is a cloud-based data platform that supports an open solution to the integration of third party services addressing building facilities management: ranging from the extraction of performance indications from monitored data, through HVAC system fault detection & diagnosis, to energy use forecasting and options for change appraisal – all aimed at improving operational performance and thereby moving closer to the original design intent. By simplifying the procedure for new service connection, the platform will support initiatives by small and medium sized companies, who face major challenges to penetrate a market dominated by large providers of building energy management systems.

Figure 1: Elements of the Hit2Gap platform

Figure 1 depicts the elements of the Hit2Gap platform and the services that may be invoked on the basis of data ‘mash-ups’ delivered on request to a particular service. The platform comprises three distinct levels:

- **field level**, encapsulating sensors and systems for data acquisition, with support for a variety of data acquisition protocols;
- **core level**, handling data exchange between modules, storing data from measurements and providing basic functionalities (e.g. data anonymization and pre-processing); and
- **management level**, comprising services that help to improve operational performance.

There are two approaches to collection and uploading of data to the platform. These are also outlined in Figure 1. The first approach is to use a ‘middleware platform’ to provide a wide set of data services and a set of Application Programming Interfaces (API) that guarantee the necessary access points for the application to access and use collected data. This has been achieved by using a commercial IoT Enterprise Grade platform (Plat. One) which provides the necessary data connector to each building. By this means, users of HIT2GAP transfer data from their system to the platform, whether they are using existing or new protocols. The second approach is by direct connection from a BMS to HIT2GAP whereby the platform provides all the necessary tools to integrate directly with a BMS system or other data sources, avoiding any intermediate level.

Conclusions

The Hit2Gap project is in its final year and this paper has presented developments to date regarding the connection of cloud-based simulation and other services to a core data. The workflow defined for these simulations (i.e. model acquisition, calibration, performance assessment) proved to be adequate to support the development of decision support systems for building operation.

The use of a new model calibration tool, Calibro, provides an automated approach to BPS model calibration. This feature represents a major shift from current practice in the field and provides a contribution to the use of simulation in the operational stage of buildings.

The use of automatic performance assessment provides access to sophisticated simulation scenarios with minimum user input. The approach does however pose new challenges as it requires the embedding of domain knowledge alongside simulation procedures to facilitate analysis that supports decision-making. Service users can concentrate on building performance issues rather than expending effort and resources on complex ad hoc model calibration and simulation process control.

The openness of the Hit2Gap platform supports the deployment of new simulation services, fostering the development of functionalities and applications tailored to address challenges in the improvement of the operation performance of large estates.

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This paper was compiled from text from the following sources and reference materials from various HIT2GAP project and review meetings:

1. HIT2GAP website – www.hit2gap.eu
2. Hit2Gap Project: Highly Innovative building control Tools, Tackling the energy performance gap, R2M - Andrea Costa, Marco Pietrobon, and Thomas Messervey – paper submitted to CLIMA 2019 – Bucharest (May 26 – 29) currently under review.
3. A 'big data' approach to the application of building performance simulation to improve the operational performance of large estates - Energy Systems Research Unit, University of Strathclyde - Joe Clarke, Daniel Costola, Andrew Cowie, Jon Hand, Nick Kelly, Filippo Monari – Proceedings of the 15th IBPSA Conference San Francisco, CA, USA, Aug. 7-9, 2017, pp 2430-2437, ISBN: 978-1-7750520-0-5

References

1. International Organization for Standardization, ISO 50001 - Energy management (2018)

The Hit2GAP Partners are:

For more detailed information about HIT2GAP visit www.hit2gap.eu. ■